

THE COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES

Shaping a Foundation for the Future

Special Insert to the
1993 CLR Annual Report

Prepared for
the Council on Library Resources
by Robert Gurwitt

SHAPING A FOUNDATION FOR THE FUTURE

These are unsettled times for libraries. Pushed by the breakneck advance of the information society, they are being forced to redefine their place in our universities and cities. A changing economy is driving them to examine whether structures they developed in the industrial age are appropriate for a new era. Shifting social values are moving them to explore new ways of serving their communities. New technologies are revolutionizing the way scholars and ordinary citizens find and use information, but are also compelling libraries to reassess their place in a society beguiled by the meteoric growth of the information business.

This is also a time of unrelenting financial strain. Academic and research libraries face growing pressure to install expensive new electronic networks and databases at the same time that the cost of traditional publications is rising—all while their parent institutions struggle through increasingly perilous financial straits. Many public libraries have been forced to close branches, lay off staff, and slash their acquisitions budgets.

As Richard De Gennaro, the librarian of Harvard College, puts it, “The challenge we’re facing right now is we have to maintain the traditional library, because that’s where most of the action is, and while we’re doing that we have to cope with new technology and the growing variety of research resources, and we have to do both of these things at a time when the total resources available to us are diminishing, in an environment that is resistant to the drastic changes we need to make to survive.”

These are daunting tasks. To be sure, libraries over the years have been enormously resourceful in adapting new technology and new ways of thinking to their work; despite limited funds, they have learned how to share isolated resources, ease public access to their collections, streamline their management, and cut costs. This, though, is an era of unaccustomed change and of bewildering financial choices. Even for libraries that are at home with innovation, the challenges ahead are staggering.

That is where the Council on Library Resources comes in. **Since 1956, the Council has been a central player in the evolution of the library world.** It has bolstered the training of skillful and imaginative library administrators, stimulated the development of new technologies for preserving materials and disseminating knowledge, focused attention on the nuts and bolts of management and library economics, funded pioneering efforts to improve communication among libraries and to transform scholarship, and encouraged revolutionary gains in users’ access to information. For the better part of four decades the Council has been an ally, adviser, and catalyst for change among libraries. With libraries moving toward so uncertain a future, it is not surprising that the Council is needed to play those roles with renewed vigor.

Doing so is especially important just now, when the social consensus that once supported libraries appears to be unraveling. This country has been turning its back on its libraries. Cities have slashed their library budgets. The federal government has proposed severing its support. Universities not only have cut funding for their own libraries, but have taken aim at the future of libraries by closing their library schools. Foundations have turned their attention to other problems.

Libraries are not, of course, uniquely burdened; there are few public institutions that haven’t found themselves in similar straits during the last few years. But ignoring the health of libraries is a bit like ignoring the health of schools: it can help the bottom line in the short term, but it exacts a great cost down the road. That is because, like schools, libraries hold the keys to the future. As former President Jimmy Carter told the American Library Association’s 1993 convention, “The best single focal point of learning on a continuing basis...[is] the libraries of the United States.”

As most citizens seem to grasp intuitively, libraries are among the few institutions that remain bulwarks in this day and age against the degradation of public space.

Academic libraries, in the face of growing budget pressure on universities to foster proprietary research owned by its funders, have remained dedicated to the notion that the profit-making potential of knowledge is irrelevant to whether or not it should be collected or made available. Public libraries have struggled to remain accessible to anyone and everyone who needs information or seeks knowledge.

Why is that access important? The reason is simple: libraries supply the necessary tools and knowledge to those who would solve society's problems, and they do so regardless of the problem's size or who wants to solve it. They hold the books that help unemployed laborers retrain themselves, they keep the statistics that buttress arguments at city council meetings, they undergird researchers trying to cure cancer or stop a tuberculosis epidemic. A library is not an institution that stands apart from the university that houses it or the city that supports it; libraries are part of those communities' warp and weft, their assurance that they can always refine and enrich themselves.

"Libraries are called into being by people who have need of them. They don't initiate themselves," says Dr. William N. Hubbard, Jr. (a former president of Upjohn Company and member of the Board of Regents of the National Library of Medicine, and a member of the CLR board of directors). "It's a fool's errand to deal with libraries as if they were institutions that hung, like Mohammed's coffin, between heaven and earth." In a very real sense, unless libraries can sort through the particular challenges that face them, it is hard to imagine that society will be able to address with any confidence the problems that confront it as a whole.

The William & Flora Hewlett Foundation, in its 1977 annual report, found another way of saying the same thing. Explaining its funding choices—which currently include the Council—the foundation argued that "making ours an effective democratic society, a society whose institutions work, is essential to human welfare not only in the United States but throughout the world." Simply put, it is the Council's job to ensure that libraries are institutions that work.

Though the Council is an operating foundation, which means that it can initiate projects as well as make grants to others, it has never had enough money to solve libraries' problems on its own, or even to fund entirely others' efforts to do so. Rather, it has wisely laid down the seed capital for projects designed to help librarianship mature. It has always recognized that the big issues facing the field are in fact made up of smaller fragments, and that progress entails finding and tackling the pieces that will advance the whole.

It is uniquely equipped to do so. It is, for one thing, small in size and able to act quickly when needed—as, for example, when a national effort to send English-language books to students and universities in China shortly after the Tiananmen Square uprising was in danger of faltering when its funding for publicity suddenly fell through; within a week, the Council had mustered the needed money.

While the Council has coordinated large and complex projects, it is also able to pay attention to the small projects—the research papers, travel expenses, and conferences—that tend to get lost in larger funding organizations. Its ability to focus on the details of librarianship has made it the vehicle of choice for funders interested in nurturing libraries and scholarship.

Just as important, it is independent of any particular institution, a virtue that has given the Council a number of strengths. It is able to steer its resources to projects that, even when carried out by a single institution, will benefit libraries as a whole. Because it is independent, it can be a neutral broker and mediator, able to convene organizations and advisers to address issues that cross institutional lines or arouse controversy. And its standing within the field draws attention to the problems it identifies—the Council's sponsorship of projects in the past has invariably given them wider notice and the credibility to marshal additional support. That is due in part to the character of the Council's board of directors, which includes not only members of the library profession, but distinguished academics and researchers who represent the public's interest in libraries.

All of this has given the Council an outsized impact for an organization of its scale. "If you ask any number of people about the half dozen most important events in librarianship, without exception you will find the Council in back of them," says William Crowe, who is dean of the University of Kansas Libraries. "You'll find the Council there in the shadows, on the sidelines, cheering people on, providing them a stipend or getting something published or funding a meeting. They make it possible for other people's ideas to come to the fore. They're a midwife."

As academic, research, and public libraries start coming to terms with the demands of the rapidly changing environments in which they work, an organization like the Council would have to be invented if it didn't already exist. As Richard De Gennaro wrote a few years back, "At the beginning of this era, our field was characterized by stability and continuity. Now it is characterized by change, discontinuity, and opportunity." In that somewhat chaotic atmosphere, someone has to stand behind the pathfinders, equipping them, urging them on, and making sure the results of their work have the impact they deserve. That is the Council's role.

It has been so since the beginning. In some ways, the Council was born into an environment much like the current one. The mid-1950s were a time of enormous ferment for librarians. It was becoming abundantly clear that new technologies—and especially the computer—were rewriting their traditional ways of doing business. Scientific and technical advances, and the competition with the Soviets, were bringing new scrutiny to the entire American educational system and to libraries' place within it. The leading edge of the Baby Boom was approaching its early teens; clearly, within a decade college and university libraries would be facing unprecedented demands on their resources.

It was in that atmosphere that Louis Wright, director of the Folger Shakespeare Library in Washington, D.C., was asked by the Ford Foundation to convene two meetings in early 1955. Ford was interested in improving libraries overall and in the role the computer would play within them. It also wanted to find

some way of escaping a growing shower of library-related funding requests. For their part, Wright and the extraordinary collection of leading librarians, archivists, historians, and academics that he convened were interested both in where libraries were headed in general and in the particulars of how they were to get there.

There are not many accounts of those gatherings in the wood-paneled stillness of the Folger Library. What exists is written in the stilted, colorless language of conference minutes. But it is clear that the discussion was wide-ranging and, reading between the lines, occasionally heated; they talked about such issues as cooperation among libraries, the problems of college and smaller public libraries, how to assess the promise of computers and microfilm, and how to promote greater access to libraries' collections. The one notion that seemed to draw universal support was the need for a national commission of some sort to coordinate efforts to find the answers to those questions.

Not surprisingly, then, that is what emerged. The Council came into existence in September 1956 as a fully funded project of the Ford Foundation; it continued to draw most of its funding from Ford until 1977. Its first president was Verner Clapp, until then the chief assistant Librarian of Congress. Its charge was expansive: "To aid in the solution of library problems."

In the decades since then, the Council has had four presidents. Clapp, a widely read, congenial man of extraordinary enthusiasm, became perhaps the leading force for change in the library world during his tenure. Fred Cole, a historian and university president, was more muted but no less influential than Clapp—"Because he was a master at working through others," commented one eulogist after his death, "his trail is more often than not blazed only by his shadow." Warren J. Haas, the former director of libraries at the University of Pennsylvania and then vice president and university librarian of Columbia University, was a driving force, both before he arrived at the Council and after, for upgrading the professional standards of

librarianship. Since 1991, W. David Penniman, a former vice president of the OCLC Online Computer Library Center and former director of the Information Services Group at AT&T Bell Laboratories, has led the Council.

Because each leader put his own imprint on the Council, it is tempting to tell its story chronologically. But more than most institutions, foundations are judged by how they respond to the needs they encounter in their chosen world. In the Council's case, its story is inextricable from the evolving challenges facing the country's libraries—especially the academic and research libraries on which it has focused much of its attention.

If there is a single theme that characterizes the evolution of libraries over the last few decades, it has been the pressure to knit scattered resources into a web linking one library to another, and all into a whole. Libraries arose, in a sense, as islands of information, each with its own cataloging systems and procedures. Left to their own devices they would undoubtedly, like island cultures everywhere, have developed exotic languages understandable only to themselves. That might have been fine if each library in the country had all the books, journals, manuscripts, and tapes ever created, but they don't. In a society that relies as heavily as ours on information, sharing it has been an imperative; that, in turn, has depended on libraries learning to communicate with one another.

From its beginnings the Council has pondered how to make it possible for libraries separated by physical distance nonetheless to share knowledge: indexes of manuscript collections, say, or cataloging information on books to be published, or a database maintained by one library but available to many. Some of the projects it funded along those lines were the best the technology of the time could offer. One of its first grants, for instance, went to the compilers of an updated *Union List of Serials*, an immense, five-volume catalog detailing the serials—some of them dating back to the eighteenth century—held by 956 libraries in the U.S. and Canada.

It was a prodigiously ambitious undertaking that, thanks also in great measure to the Council, was on its way to being outmoded by the time it was published in 1965.

For the Council also realized early on that the future of libraries lay with the computer, both as a labor-saving device and, ultimately, as a means of sharing information. It is no exaggeration to say that anyone who sits down at a terminal today to ferret out material on a particular subject—for a school paper or a biomedical research program or a neighborhood economic development project—is using the fruit of seeds sown by the Council.

A perfect example is MEDLARS. It is a computer-based information service maintained by the National Library of Medicine (NLM) that not only gives its users access to an immense array of data on medical research and published articles, but can provide a patient with lists of, say, cancer specialists in any city or region in the country or give emergency workers details of the toxic effects of a particular chemical spill. It is the largest library-based information system in the country, a cornerstone of both medical research and practice, and its roots lie in a grant the Council made in 1958 to the NLM to plan for the automation of its main bibliographic service. Without that pivotal early step, says Dr. Martin Cummings, who was for two decades the NLM's director and now sits on the Council's board, MEDLARS would not have followed. "People think of this as a great big government invention," he says. "But the fact is, the Library couldn't have started on it without that little grant from the Council."

Seed money for other projects has affected not just particular library programs, but the entire library world. Over the years, the Council has funded work to develop national and international automation standards and cataloging rules, made it possible for work to begin on a worldwide system for the organized exchange of bibliographic information, and helped create a comprehensive, computerized database of serial publications—no small feat, since journals and magazines, unlike

books, often change names and publishers over the course of their history.

Probably no set of Council projects has had greater impact on American libraries than its grants to the Library of Congress; taken as a whole, they have helped that institution shoulder the central role it plays today, saving the country's libraries hundreds of millions of dollars each year in cataloging costs. The Council helped the Library automate its services, funded its work on developing a national database of serial publications, and supported its efforts over the years to develop the Cataloging in Publication Program, which allows cataloging information to be included in books as they are published.

One of the Council's most significant sets of grants was to the Library's Machine-Readable Cataloging (MARC) program, which was a crucial step—if not the crucial step—in the development of a national database of cataloging records. Its goal was to make it easy and inexpensive for libraries around the country to automate their procedures by acquiring basic cataloging information about books—details such as their titles, publishers, and authors, as well as the subjects they covered—from a central source.

Before MARC's development during the 1960s, libraries either created their own catalog record for each item that came in, or depended on huge prepared catalogs of card images that they transcribed for their own system or copied and used directly. There were two problems with this approach: it was cumbersome and time-consuming; and it meant that as libraries automated, each had to develop its own computer format for keeping track of its holdings, which was fine for individual libraries but meant a programming nightmare once they started trying to share information.

Through a series of grants from the Council during the 1960s, however, the Library of Congress was able to start building a system that would, in essence, give libraries a common language for cataloging. It launched the full-scale MARC service in 1969, allowing libraries to slash their costs by cutting the amount of

original cataloging that had to be done and providing them with the raw data to produce their own catalog cards and book catalogs. Just as important, with its introduction of a common computer language for libraries, MARC made it possible for the first time to envision a nationwide system for keeping track of their holdings.

It might help to pause a moment here to put these developments in perspective. It's easy to see why computerizing their procedures was a good thing for libraries: it saved time, money, and effort. What is crucial to understand, though, is how enormously vital it has also been to ordinary library users.

The reason is that information is useless unless you can get to it. That, in turn, means keeping it on hand and knowing how to find it. Anything that helps librarians store or retrieve information, in other words, gives ordinary citizens better access to it. By setting a national bibliographic system as a goal—and more importantly, by funding the unglamorous steps, such as MARC, needed to make it a reality—the Council was in essence trying to make it possible for anyone, anywhere in the country, to find out which resources could meet their needs and how to lay their hands on them.

Still, it took some time, and a concerted effort, to make that goal a reality. The project that made it possible was the Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP), which many librarians rank among the most important of the Council's ventures.

At its heart, the problem the BSDP had to resolve was not technical, but political. With the development of the MARC format, in the late 1960s and early 1970s a number of regional library networks sprang up to provide bibliographic services to their members. Where once only the Library of Congress had provided catalog cards to subscribers around the country, suddenly there was a host of organizations—the Ohio College Library Center, the Southeastern Library Network, the New England Library Network and others—using MARC to create not only catalog cards, but a range of services including, most importantly, online access to biblio-

graphic information. Each organization had been born to meet a particular regional need, so there was no guiding hand behind the activity—although the Council did its best to play a coordinating role by providing funding and advice for projects that might resolve general problems of network development.

Over time, the Ohio group (now the OCLC Online Computer Library Center) and a consortium of the country's research libraries, known as the Research Libraries Group (RLG), came to dominate the field, each possessing enormous databases of bibliographic records. The two large groups competed intensely for members, with the result that libraries connected with one or the other often refused to cooperate with their rival's subscribers. While the ability to tie together every one of the country's research and academic libraries existed in theory, in practice it was a thorny diplomatic problem.

Launched by the Council in 1978, the BSDP became the neutral ground on which the competing organizations could meet and hammer out ways to link up their databases. Its importance to research can be gauged in part by the list of funders that supported it, something of a Who's Who of organizations active in the library field at the time: the National Endowment for the Humanities, the Carnegie Corporation, the Commonwealth Fund, the Ford Foundation, the William and Flora Hewlett Foundation, the Lilly Endowment, the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, and the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation.

The program was enormous in its scope, pursuing nine separate areas of endeavor and calling on the talents not just of research librarians, but of computer and communications specialists and of senior academic and industry officials. It established sets of standards not just for bibliographic records kept by the different systems, but for communicating among them. It focused on improving the bibliographic databases themselves by helping to computerize records held only on microfilm and microfiche and to develop a plan for converting records that could be found only on paper. It set up a project to find ways of linking the databases

to each other and of making the links seamless to users. And, perhaps most important, it explored the range of services that researchers, scholars, scientists, students, and others would need in order to make full use of the available databases. The result was an online system that allows a user, from a single terminal, to search the major bibliographic databases in the country.

Since those databases contain information on most resources held by this country's libraries, it is now possible for anyone with access to a terminal to find almost every piece of cataloged material held somewhere in a library. He or she can delve into the New York Public Library's resources on the economics of inner-city hospitals, for instance, or piece together the history of attempts to regulate bank redlining from around the country, or find the musings of scientists worldwide on extraterrestrial biology. Small wonder that any number of librarians consider the BSDP, in the words of one, "the greatest library development in this century."

As important as improving access to this country's library collections has been, though, it is only one side of the coin. The other is building and maintaining those collections in the first place. The Council has never had enough money to help individual libraries acquire materials, but it has routinely funded projects to resolve problems faced by all them. It helped the American Library Association (ALA) set up the Library Technology Project, which developed new products not available from commercial sources and helps libraries judge those products that are. It provided the seed money for one of the tools most used by college libraries in guiding the development of their collections, the ALA monthly *Choice*, which provides short scholarly evaluations of books as they appear. And over the years it has helped ALA study the insurance requirements of libraries, survey the strengths and weaknesses of public library systems, and study the financing of online services run by public libraries.

One of the Council's key ventures has been its sponsorship over the decades of a large-scale effort to preserve printed material or its intellectual content—an undertaking that is in no small part responsible for the widespread recognition that our knowledge base needs to be protected. It was not always so; when the Council first formed, only a handful of people paid much regard to the notion that the country was in danger of allowing its collected wisdom to crumble into dust. One of them, fortunately, was Verner Clapp.

The creation of the Council was, in some ways, a godsend for Clapp in this regard, since it gave him a vehicle for seeing to it that preservation work got under way. Although the Ford Foundation was interested primarily in issues relating to automation, Clapp argued forcefully that as important as computers might be to libraries, so, too, were paper, binders, ink, and, in particular, the ability to preserve images on microfilm. He set the Council on a course of promoting both the technology of preserving the human record and the urgency of doing so.

Over its first few decades, the Council had far more success with the first task than with the second. It funded the research of pioneering preservationist William J. Barrow, who demonstrated that it was acid in the paper used for manufacturing books since the mid-19th century—and not environmental pollution, as was popularly believed at the time—that was the prime culprit in its deterioration. The Council also helped Barrow set up a laboratory that developed standards of paper durability and investigated methods both of deacidifying paper and of manufacturing acid-free paper. It helped the Library of Congress establish its Preservation Research Laboratory, funded the first regional conservation center (in New England), underwrote studies of particular technical problems and guides for conservators, and subsidized the development of microform technology as the most promising avenue for safeguarding the intellectual content of deteriorating publications.

By the late 1970s, in short, people concerned with preservation knew what had to be done. Making it

happen was another matter. For a variety of reasons, publishers hesitated to adopt acid-free paper, and paper manufacturers were slow to make it. Library directors had their minds on other problems. The people who in the end would have to fund preservation work—university administrators, foundation executives, and the like—seemed unaware of the problem. As much as 80 percent of the collections of the country's premier libraries—basically, anything printed after 1865—was in danger of falling to pieces.

It was around this time that Warren J. Haas took over as the Council's third president. Haas had seen the effects of deterioration on research collections firsthand, and once at the Council's helm he used the position as a bully pulpit to preach the cause. "If individuals have any sense of the importance of the continuity of the human experience, they can't avoid the problem of preservation of the human record," he said in *Slow Fires*, a 1987 film that aired on public television and that the Council funded in an effort to build a national constituency for attacking the problem. "To fail to do so is, in a sense, to turn your back on history."

During the 1980s, Haas and the Council made sure no backs remained turned for long. They mustered a broad cross section of the library, university, and foundation communities on behalf of preservation efforts. They brought about the creation of a committee on book longevity to make recommendations on how to produce longer-lasting printed materials. They encouraged the creation of a modern standard for acid-free paper. In 1981 they helped establish a preservation task force as part of a joint project of the Council and the Association of American Universities. They spurred the creation of a mid-Atlantic microfilming facility dedicated to quality preservation and eventually, in 1986, set up a national commission to deal with the problem. Initially funded, staffed, and organized by the Council, the Commission on Preservation and Access became a separate nonprofit organization in 1988. Preservation had finally come of age.

In the end, if maintaining and ensuring access to collections are pieces of the same puzzle, then someone has to be able to put them together. For this reason, the Council has worked from the beginning to help research and academic libraries develop their operations and management strengths.

Its efforts on this score have fallen into three broad groupings: professional development, management issues, and strategic planning. In 1968, the Council began its first fellowship program, designed to give librarians a chance to pursue independent projects aimed at exploring administrative and technical frontiers; the program lasted more than a decade, and funded 199 fellowships in all.

Two other Council programs have been influential. Its Academic Library Management Intern Program, begun in 1974, gave librarians with the potential to become leaders in the field a chance to spend a year working with colleagues at the top of the profession. Only a few interns were chosen each year, and many of this country's research and academic library directors have passed through the program on the way to their current positions. In 1981, the Council also funded a program at the University of California, Los Angeles, to give specialized training to recently appointed senior managers of major library systems; there have been ninety-seven such senior fellows through 1993.

The Council's focus on management began with a 1969 grant to the Association of Research Libraries (ARL) for a Booz, Allen & Hamilton study of management practices in university libraries. That in turn led to one of the longer-lasting and more influential developments in the field, the creation in 1970 of the Office of University Library Management Studies (now the Office of Management Services, or OMS) within ARL.

Until then, there had been no agency dedicated to helping research libraries develop as organizations or to giving them the tools for moving into a new period of focused delivery of information services. With consistent funding from the Council for its first decade, OMS has created programs to analyze management structures, collections, services, and preservation planning;

it has designed training programs for key library staff; and it has looked for pioneering programs—dealing with anything from marketing library services to appraising library performance—and described them in kits designed to help other libraries innovate. With help from the Council, ARL has also built an initiative to apply the findings and benefits of OMS programs to smaller college and university libraries.

Throughout the last few decades, the Council has also been investing small sums of money in studies to understand better the microeconomics of library services and to develop methods for libraries to measure their performance. It has funded studies of the costs of computerization and microfilming, the feasibility of public libraries providing books by mail, formulas for library administrators to use in projecting future growth, methods for auditing the finances of university libraries, the costs of decision support systems, savings from copy cataloging, the costs of online catalogs, methods of strategic planning and budgeting, the actual costs and benefits involved in interlibrary loan programs....The list goes on.

As useful to the profession as all these projects and studies have been in the past, it is becoming clear that their real value may lie down the road, in the foundation they've laid for a far more ambitious set of management-related efforts. For if libraries are to survive, much less prosper, in a hard-edged economy, they must pay close attention to what their operations cost and whether they can be better structured. In essence, they will have to build an economic case for their existence and then redesign themselves to buttress it.

Building on the work it has sponsored in the past, the Council has convened a study group on the microeconomics of library operations, supported the development of a set of seminars for librarians on the precepts of total quality management, and funded strategic planning programs at four universities and university systems designed to look at the particulars of library operations and how they fit into their larger institutional aims. At Rutgers University, it is funding a project to analyze the economic benefits provided by research libraries to their parent institutions.

The detailed management information those projects should provide is only a beginning, though. For while the last few decades' work has given libraries an increasingly sophisticated set of tools with which to carry out their missions, it could not give them detailed blueprints for meeting the needs of a society that is changing as rapidly as ours. In every area with which the Council concerns itself—improving information processing and access, developing libraries' infrastructure, understanding library economics and management, and strengthening their human resources—libraries stand on the threshold of daunting, but potentially exhilarating, change. If they are to be institutions that work—if academic libraries are to serve universities and research institutions, and public libraries are to help their communities grow and regenerate themselves—then there are frontiers that must be explored without delay.

While those frontiers may differ somewhat for academic and public libraries, they involve the same forces: the challenges and opportunities posed by new technology, and the changing needs and wants of the communities served. How libraries of all sorts come to grips with the pressures they are facing will have profound implications for their management, their structures, and their personnel.

It is becoming clear to academic and research librarians, for instance, that new information and telecommunications technology is not only changing how libraries operate, but may also transform their place within their parent institutions. Research on that front is still young, but three ventures underwritten in part by the Council highlight the potential.

At Rice University, the Council is funding a project uniting librarians, computer scientists, and faculty members to develop undergraduate courses using hypertext multimedia. The aim is in part to familiarize students with the technology, but it will also undoubtedly change the way classes are taught, involving librarians up front in their design.

The Council is also underwriting an effort to create a national engineering library that will exist only in

virtual form. At the moment, the information that engineers need to call on is widely scattered—in formal published literature, in government technical reports, in the trade literature and reports on ongoing projects, and in catalogs and manuals of standards. There is no efficient way for an engineer sitting down to plan a project or build a manufacturing process to find it all. The current venture is designed to build a “library” out of those various pieces and tie them together in an easily accessible network. An engineer who sits down at a terminal will be able to obtain whatever information he or she needs, whether it comes from the data banks of a commercial publisher or a professional society or an actual library.

In another effort that has extraordinary potential for both librarians and academics, the Council is working with librarians and researchers exploring a concept known as “knowledge management” that in the last few years has begun to tantalize the profession. The need for a new information model has been evident within the scientific research community for years. The amount of time required to publish results in print has made prompt communication hard for scientists and scholars. And while scientists trying to cope with the problem have created discipline-based knowledge networks, they have done so in a chaotic manner, often working on their own with no general standards to guide them; scholarly communication is, as a result, quicker, but not necessarily any more efficient. The idea of knowledge management is that it will play a coordinating and integrating role—much as, in an earlier and simpler manner, MARC set the standard for sharing information among libraries.

Some initial work on this score was begun a few years ago at Johns Hopkins University's Welch Medical Library in a Council-supported effort to transform a printed volume on human genetics into an electronic knowledge base that is accessible to—and can be updated by—geneticists worldwide. Working in conjunction with that ongoing venture, the library at the University of California at San Francisco has launched an effort to provide its researchers and physicians with

online access to journal articles as they are published, and to collaborative and peer-review networks.

As compelling as such projects are, though, they raise as many questions as they answer. The advent of sophisticated communications technologies means that new financial relationships among libraries, publishers, online networks, and the vendors of services and equipment will have to be erected in a manner that makes economic sense for them all. Libraries and publishers still have to work out who owns information and how, in an age when data arrives in a constant stream, it is to be maintained and upgraded for library users.

And that is only the tip of the iceberg. For academic and research librarians themselves there are a host of nettlesome puzzles. The rising cost of publications and of collecting electronic data has made it evident that no single library can hope to own everything; resources will have to be shared. But who holds what, how it's made available, and how it's paid for remain uncertain. For that matter, the sheer growth in the availability of knowledge and the speed with which it is being produced are challenging libraries' ability to handle it all.

As they make more use of innovative technology, academic and research libraries are also finding that meeting their users' needs is growing more complicated. Not only do scholars in the humanities work differently from those in the sciences, but some find the pace of change in the tools available for research deeply unsettling, while others chafe at libraries' deliberation in adopting them. As libraries find themselves pressed to reallocate scarce funding to new resources, they are having trouble maintaining their acquisition of books and periodicals, and so are drawing the anger of their more tradition-minded users. If they are to meet their users' needs, in other words, libraries will clearly have to launch a concerted effort to study them more closely.

Nor are academic libraries alone in facing change; so are the librarians who help them function. There is mounting pressure on them to be specialists in their respective academic fields, which in turn is requiring an

entirely new way of looking at the training required for information professionals. The problem is that some of the leading library schools in the country have either been shut down recently or are threatened with closure, making it unclear how that challenge will be met. Academic librarians now face the problem of promoting libraries' cause not just within their parent institutions, but within the scholarly world as a whole.

For public libraries, adapting to the changing needs of the communities they serve and to the growth of the information society is proving equally disruptive. Public libraries have been forced to decide how to respond to towns and cities grappling with demographic change, cultural diversity, changing families, shifting economies and job markets, a fraying social order, stressed neighborhoods, and decaying infrastructure. Over the last few years, many libraries have moved to tackle those issues head-on, working with community groups to explore what specific information they need to do their jobs, or establishing adult literacy programs, after-school reading programs for latchkey children, and reading kits for new mothers.

As crucial as those efforts are, though, they raise unfamiliar dilemmas for librarians. Limited resources mean that for every new program that is developed, a traditional library function tends to suffer. Librarians steeped in the practice of collection development are not accustomed to becoming community outreach workers overnight. Politicians used to thinking of libraries as a safely innocuous service don't always take it kindly when they become agents of community change.

Library directors trying to push their institutions in new directions are groping their way through all of these developments with no models to follow, few precepts to guide them, and a host of questions that need to be answered. If, for instance, they are to serve a culturally diverse clientele, do they have enough understanding of the cultures their clients represent to provide them with adequate service? And if libraries can play a role in advancing literacy and furthering economic development, how can they do so without threatening their

ability to deliver the materials that people want? Answering those questions will entail not just learning more about public libraries' users and their needs and wants, but learning which yardsticks to use in measuring success: is it the size of a collection that counts, or the savings to society of making sure that an illiterate child does not grow up to become an illiterate adult?

As with academic and research libraries, new technology is bringing benefits and dilemmas in equal measure. On the one hand, it is making libraries more accessible to people they have never been able to reach in the past, and is giving library patrons a chance to do research that would be impossible otherwise. On the other hand, the managerial questions raised by technology are no easier than those raised by community responsibility. Technology costs money, but if public libraries start charging a fee for such services, what will be the impact on their historic role of providing free, equal access to information? What should the library's role be in avoiding a community separated into those who can afford information and those who cannot? As libraries develop networks that link them to each other, should they invest local tax dollars in developing databases that might eventually become available to anyone in the state, or even the country?

As Eleanor Jo (Joey) Rodger, director of the Urban Libraries Council, puts it, "It's not that technology spells the doom of the public library, it's that we need to understand the core of the business we're in as a publicly funded distribution system, identify the factors that affect the distribution system in the private and public sectors, and figure out how to ensure public funding for that chunk of it that is in the public interest."

These are questions with which, until recently, the Council probably would not have concerned itself; historically, it has focused much of its attention on academic and research libraries, believing that it could make its greatest contribution by helping them develop an infrastructure of knowledge that would then become freely accessible to all. But that is no longer enough.

The urgency of addressing the issues facing libraries of all sorts and the potential that technology brings for linking public to academic libraries create a need for an organization that can serve the library field as a whole. That is what the Council has set out to do.

In helping libraries tame these frontiers, the Council will be relying on the experience it has acquired over the decades since its beginning. It knows how to identify promising projects and lend its authority to make sure they get the attention they deserve. It is practiced at seeking path-breaking work that can point the way for the bulk of the library community to follow. It understands how to bring libraries and funders together, and how to articulate areas of concern that others, with greater resources, can address. And it has gained the wisdom to ensure that the work it funds illuminates the needs that libraries themselves must address if they are to strengthen their contributions to the people they serve.

All of the hard questions posed to libraries by the new information order and by the social changes they must grapple with are also opportunities. Libraries have the potential to become gateways to the vast information resources that this country needs to move forward with confidence; more than any other institution in society, they are equipped to make them available to the largest possible audience. In the end, just as the Council itself is a catalyst for progress among libraries, so it can help libraries to be catalysts in their turn, assisting current and future generations of citizens in becoming independent problem solvers with the knowledge and the information they need to overcome any challenge.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES

SELECTED CHRONOLOGY OF PROJECTS

1956 Ford Foundation establishes the Council

1957 First of many grants to American Library Association to establish and support the Library Technology Project, a continuing program of research, testing, and standardization of library materials and equipment

First of many grants to William J. Barrow and the Barrow Laboratory for investigations relating to the preservation of books and permanence of book papers; eventually determined causes of paper deterioration and developed permanent/durable book papers

1958 Grant to National Library of Medicine to mechanize *Current List of Medical Literature (Index Medicus)*, which resulted in MEDLARS

First of several grants to Library of Congress to create *National Union Catalog of Manuscript Collections*

First of several grants made over a 35-year period to the Library of Congress to investigate the feasibility of, develop, implement, and subsequently evaluate the Cataloging in Publication Program

1959 First of several grants for preparation of the third and final edition of *Union List of Serials in Libraries of the United States and Canada*, supplemented by *New Serial Titles*

1960 Grant to International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) for international conference on cataloging that resulted in the "Paris Principles," an agreement on uniformity of practice

1961 With the National Science Foundation, CLR begins long-term support of American National Standards Institute (ANSI) Committee Z39 on Library Work, Documentation, and Related Publishing Practices, which develops standards for practices and methods in the field of library work, in the preparation and utilization of documents, and in those aspects of publishing that affect library methods and use

Grant to the American Library Association to launch *Choice*, a monthly book-selection service for academic and public libraries

1964 Publication of CLR-funded report on possibilities for automation at the Library of Congress

1965 Grant to the Library of Congress to facilitate the establishment of the *National Register of Microform Masters*

1966 Funding provided for a machine-readable cataloging (MARC) feasibility study and for catalog data studies to create specific procedures required for the distribution products

Grant to enable Richard Smith to develop a non-aqueous deacidification method for paper preservation

1967 Grants to the New England Board of Higher Education to explore the application of MARC tapes for library cooperation; followed by a 1971 grant to study feasibility of transferring the Ohio College Library Center (OCLC) system to other groups of libraries

Books for College Libraries (ALA) is published with CLR support

Anglo-American Cataloging Rules is published with CLR support

1968 Beginning of CLR Fellowship Program, which provided research opportunities for librarians for over a decade; followed by Faculty/Librarian Cooperative Research Program, which continues to the present

1969 Project MARC (later MARC Distribution Service), funded by CLR, begins the sale of magnetic tapes containing cataloging information in a standard format, including all English-language monographs cataloged by the Library of Congress

CLR and the National Endowment for the Humanities begin ten-year College Library Program, designed to bring the library into a central role in the education of undergraduates

1970 First of several grants by CLR and the U.S. Office of Education to help OCLC develop its computerized regional library system

Association of Research Libraries' Office of Management Services (OMS) is established with CLR funding

1971 International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA), with support from CLR through 1981, establishes permanent secretariat for its Committee on Cataloging, which serves as a center for international coordination and standardization of cataloging rules; also establishes international system for organized exchange of bibliographical information in standard format

IFLA strengthens its headquarters secretariat with support from CLR; ongoing support enables IFLA to become the most effective vehicle of international library cooperation

1972 International Standard Serial Number (ISSN) developed from U.S. standard for serial numbering developed by CLR-supported ANSI Committee Z39; CLR staff worked for its implementation in the U.S. and internationally

CLR and the National Endowment for the Humanities provide funding for BALLOTS (ultimately the Research Libraries Information Network) to assist in bringing this automated bibliographic control system to operational status

1973 Grant to Washington Library Network (WLN) to continue development of its statewide computerized library network for regional sharing of resources

New England Document Conservation Center (later Northeast DCC) established with CLR funding

1974 CLR assumes initial management and funding role in CONSER (Conversion of Serials) program, established in order to create a comprehensive bibliographic database of serials in machine-readable form

CLR gives consultative support and grant to SOLINET, a new regional library network

CLR Academic Library Management Intern Program begins; 55 interns participate through 1993

1978 *Anglo-American Cataloguing Rules*, 2nd edition, published with CLR support

Beginning of Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP), a multi-year program with the goals of improving bibliographic products, controlling costs of technical processes in individual libraries, and improving access to information by all users

1980 CLR (BSDP) begins funding the Linked Authority Systems Project (later Linked Systems Project) to establish requirements and develop specifications for hardware and software required for telecommunications and machine interchange of records among bibliographic networks and the Library of Congress

CLR (BSDP) begins efforts to coordinate evaluation of online public access catalogs in order to produce comparative data on existing systems and guide future online catalog development

CLR (BSDP) supports investigation and development of a thesaurus for art and architecture, which becomes a model tool

1982 CLR (BSDP) provides grant to Rutgers University for the construction of an international inventory of machine-readable texts in the humanities

1983 Partial support for Association of American Publishers project to develop industrywide standards for preparing and processing electronic manuscripts

Partial support for the CONSER Abstracting & Indexing Coverage Project, managed by the Association of Research Libraries and based at the Library of Congress, to enhance serial bibliographic records

CLR creates the Committee on the Records of Government, which identified issues and recommended solutions for government records management, particularly for electronic information

1985 ANSI/NISO Z39 standard on permanent paper published; supported by CLR grant

CLR provides initial funding for Mid-Atlantic States Cooperative Preservation Service (MAPS)

1986 Publication of *Brittle Books*, reports of the CLR Committee on Preservation and Access

CLR provides support for an international Conference on Preservation of Library Materials, which launched the IFLA core program for Preservation and Conservation

Commission on Preservation and Access is established with CLR support; it becomes a separate organization in 1988

CLR publishes *The Economics of Research Libraries*, which provides library managers with information on using cost data for strategic planning, budgeting, and forecasting

1987 CLR, the Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the National Endowment for the Humanities, the Exxon Education Foundation, and the Library of Congress sponsor production of *Slow Fires*, a film calling for increased awareness of the need to preserve the human record

1988 CLR provides funds to establish an IFLA Fellows program named after Robert Vosper, CLR Board Member, which encourages interest in international aspects of librarianship and gives visibility and support to IFLA's core programs

1989 CLR hosts conference and conducts studies for the National Science Foundation to explore selected aspects of scientific and engineering communication, resulting in publication of *Communications in Support of Science and Engineering*

Support to Association of Research Libraries for studies of serial pricing

1990 CLR awards strategic planning and policy grants to Columbia University, Harvard University, the Triangle Research Libraries Network, and the State University of New York Center Libraries

1991 Grant to Urban Libraries Council for partial support of invitational seminar on public library financial practices; *Balancing the Book\$* is based on the papers and discussions, while *Keeping the Book\$* summarizes a U.S. Department of Education study on exemplary public library financial practices

Support for a Strategic Visions Steering Committee to explore issues related to the library profession in the electronic age and to draft vision and value statements for discussion with the broader library community

1992 CLR and Engineering Foundation host conference to explore the potential for developing a plan to improve the effective use of engineering information and data; the report, *Exploration of a National Engineering Information Service*, is published

Association of College and Research Libraries' College Library Director Mentor Program begins with CLR support

With the Getty Art History Information Program, the American Council of Learned Societies, the Coalition for Networked Information, and the Research Libraries Group, CLR cosponsors a conference on "Technology, Scholarship, and the Humanities"

1993 Grant to Rutgers University to develop and apply tools and procedures for measuring costs and benefits of diverse library functions

To investigate the role of the library in teaching within a multimedia environment, CLR provides partial support for a project at Rice University to develop materials for an undergraduate course within the university's electronic studio project

CLR begins concerted effort to encourage a national engineering information initiative

Council on Library Resources
1400 16th Street, N.W., Suite 510
Washington, D.C. 20036
(202) 483-7474